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The Influence of Academic Entitlement and Envy on the Spiritual Struggles of University Students and Implications for Management

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Abstract

Background: *Through their spiritual activities, students frequently look for deeper connections, which prompts them to investigate, reflect on, and occasionally confront spiritual challenges. Envy and academic entitlement are two psychological variables that might exacerbate these difficulties.*

Objective: *This study investigates the mediating role of envy on the relationship between academic entitlement and spiritual struggles.*

Methods: *The study surveyed 158 university students (58.9% female, ages 19-24, 70.3% Christian, 28.5% Muslim). Participants filled out self-report questionnaires assessing academic entitlement, envy, and spiritual struggles. The researchers analyzed the data using descriptive statistics and t-tests ($p < 0.05$).*

Results: *The study revealed that academic entitlement significantly influenced spiritual struggles, including moral struggles ($t = 3.77$), religious doubt ($t = 4.08$) and ultimate meaning struggles ($t = 3.83$). Highly entitled students exhibited higher levels of benign envy ($t = 4.08$), which in turn were associated with increased spiritual struggles. Benign envy showed a significant positive influence on spiritual struggles, demonic ($t = 3.04$), and religious doubt ($t = 3.42$). Additionally, benign envy partially mediated the relationship between academic entitlement and spiritual struggles.*

Conclusion: *The study concludes that benign envy partially plays a role in explaining the influence of academic entitlement on spiritual struggles. The findings suggest that tackling entitlement and envy could help lessen these spiritual struggles in students.*

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The Influence of Academic Entitlement and Envy on the Spiritual Struggles of University Students and Implications for Management**Introduction**

The search for meaning and purpose has become an increasingly significant aspect of human existence. People navigating the complexities of modern life are seeking a deeper connection with themselves and the world around them. This quest for connection often leads individuals to explore various spiritual practices and philosophies that offer guidance and meaning in their lives. Through this exploration, individuals may start to question their existing beliefs and values, sparking a spiritual journey towards self-discovery and personal growth. However, the path of spiritual exploration is rarely smooth. Spiritual struggle can occur when individuals experience worry, tension, conflict, or stress centered around something that people consider sacred. (Pargament & Exline, 2021). This experience can take many forms, including the six dimensions identified by Exline et al. (2014): divine struggles (abandonment, anger, and disappointment with God), demonic struggles (attributing problems to evil spirits), struggles with doubt (uncertainty and questioning religious beliefs), moral struggles (guilt and tension), ultimate meaning struggles (questioning the purpose of life), and interpersonal spiritual struggles (conflicts with others over religious matters). This experience can trigger a search for greater understanding, prompting exploration of different philosophies and spiritual practices. As individuals explore various belief systems, they may encounter conflicting ideas, leading to cognitive dissonance and a reevaluation of their core values. This reassessment can lead to personal growth and transformation (Pargament & Exline, 2021) as individuals strive to align their beliefs with their evolving understanding of spirituality. Spiritual struggle can be a

normal part of personal growth, but it can be challenging for students. The intense emotions and questioning can distract from studies, making it hard to focus. Students may feel preoccupied with existential questions, hindering information absorption, which can trigger an identity crisis. The emotional turmoil sparked by an identity crisis can lead to a sense of disconnection from oneself and others, ultimately making it more difficult to focus on academic pursuits. In fact, research has shown that greater spiritual struggles are linked to reduced life satisfaction and sadness. (Zarzycka, 2019). Social isolation often follows, as individuals who struggle more spiritually may feel disconnected from others who don't share their concerns, leading to feelings of loneliness and hindering support systems crucial for academic success. The internal turmoil caused by spiritual struggle can manifest in various ways, including suicidal thoughts, stress, depression, anxiety, addiction, and PTSD (Bockrath et al., 2021). Spiritual struggle can lead to feelings of hopelessness and disconnection from oneself and others. This disconnection can cause individuals to neglect their physical well-being, with far-reaching consequences. One such severe consequence is suicidal ideation, a disturbing finding echoed in research by Currier et al. (2017).

This study is hinged on social comparison theory. Festinger (1954) introduced the idea of social comparison theory, which contends that people are prone to assessing their own value by comparing it to that of others. It can take two forms: upward comparison and downward comparison. Upward comparison involves measuring against superiors, while downward comparison involves comparing to perceived inferiors. (Festinger, 1954).

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How students perceive their academic standing compared to others can contribute to a sense of entitlement, making this an important focus of the study. Academic entitlement is a personality trait characterized by the propensity to assume academic achievement without taking personal accountability for reaching that success (Chowning & Campbell, 2009). When students expect success without effort, they may struggle to cope with setbacks, which can lead to frustration and disappointment (Tobechi & Elvis, 2023) and lower psychological well-being (Huang, 2017). Academic entitlement is common among university students; many see themselves as paying customers who deserve good grades (Sohr-Preston & Boswell, 2015). When things don't go their way, they often blame professors instead of their own effort (Kopp & Finney, 2013). Some believe just showing up and doing most assignments should be enough to pass (Edgar et al., 2020). When reality hits, they may feel frustrated, even blaming God or others, leading to guilt, regret, and struggles with faith (Grubbs et al., 2013; Zitek & Jordan, 2019).

On the other hand, envy is another variable that might mediate this relationship. Envy is a complex emotion that arises when we compare ourselves to others and feel that they have something we lack. It can push us to improve or lead to resentment. Defined as the painful awareness of another's advantage, envy often triggers self-doubt and frustration (Merriam-Webster, 2018). It involves two people: the envied, who has the desired trait, and the envier, who feels inferior (Parrott & Smith, 1993). This feeling can damage self-esteem and lead to either motivation or hostility (Smith & Kim, 2007).

Envy takes two forms: malicious and benign. Malicious envy fuels resentment and can lead to harmful actions like gossip or sabotage

(Van de Ven et al., 2011). Benign envy, on the other hand, inspires self-improvement and effort (Lange & Crusius, 2015). In academics, entitled students may feel envious when others succeed, believing success is owed to them. This can lead to frustration, resentment, or motivation to improve (Rahaei & Salehzadeh, 2020).

Academic entitlement can fuel benign envy, motivating students to strive for self-improvement. However, this constant drive often comes from comparing themselves to others, which can lead to self-doubt, low self-esteem, and spiritual struggles (Grubbs et al., 2014; Nasidi et al., 2024). Benign envy can make spirituality feel like a competition, where external validation matters more than personal connection with a higher power (Muhamad et al., 2022). Seeing others progress faster can create doubt, resentment, and even a crisis of faith. Instead of appreciating blessings, envy shifts focus to what is lacking, deepening spiritual struggles (Kaminger et al., 2023).

There is a need for further exploration of this concept. This research closes this gap by exploring the mediating role of benign envy on the relationship between academic entitlement and spiritual struggles. We propose that benign envy plays a crucial mediating role in this relationship, serving as a bridge between academic entitlement and spiritual struggle. Specifically, we suggest that individuals with high levels of academic entitlement are more likely to experience feelings of envy towards others who have achieved greater success or recognition, which can lead to spiritual struggles such as feelings of disconnection from oneself and others.

Hypothesis

H₁: There will be a significant influence of academic entitlement on students' spiritual struggles.

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H₂: There will be a significant influence of academic entitlement on both benign and malign envy.

H₃: There will be a significant influence of benign and malign envy on spiritual struggles.

H₄: There will be a strong mediating effect of benign envy on the influence of academic entitlement on spiritual struggles.

Method

This study adopted a quantitative cross-sectional research design to explore a phenomenon without manipulating any variables. The independent variables were naturally occurring in the context, meaning the researcher had no control over their manipulation. To gather data, a questionnaire was administered to students at Nasarawa State University, Keffi. The target population consisted of over 3,000 students, and a random sample of 149 participants was selected using Yemane's formula. Out of 200 distributed questionnaires, 158 were deemed suitable for analysis. In terms of demographics, women made up the bulk of participants (58.9%), while men made up 36.1%. The other participants declined to reveal their gender. 81.6% of the participants were between the ages of 19 and 24, which was the largest age range. The bulk (70.3%) identified as Christian, and Muslims (28.5%), while the rest declined to declare their religious affiliation.

Measures

Study participants completed self-report questionnaires that gathered sociodemographic information, including age, gender, marital status, and religion. The second section consisted of 8-item Academic Entitlement Questionnaire (AEQ). Kopp et al. (2011) created the 8-item Academic Entitlement Questionnaire (AEQ), which uses a 5-point Likert scale with 1 denoting "strongly disagree" and 5 denoting "strongly agree" for each item to evaluate academic

entitlement. Strong construct validity and internal consistency were demonstrated by the scale's initial validation, which involved a sample of 1,045 undergraduate students from a mid-sized American university (Cronbach's alpha =.81). Positive associations between psychological entitlement and an external locus of control, as well as AEQ scores, demonstrated additional validity (Kopp et al., 2011). The instrument's reliability index in this investigation was $r = .74$.

In this study, envy was measured using the Benign and Malicious Envy Scale (BeMaS), which was created by Lange and Crusius (2015a). Five items make up the scale, which measures dispositional benign and malevolent envy. Several studies have demonstrated its reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values exceeding .72 and acceptable test-retest reliability (Kwiatkowska et al., 2022). According to Çırpan and Özdoğru (2017), the Cronbach alpha values for benign and malevolent envy were .85 and .89, respectively. According to Kolawele et al. (2020), the Cronbach alpha for the entire scale in Nigeria was .76, while the values for the benign and malicious subscales in the current study were .71 and .79, respectively.

Spiritual struggle was measured using the Religious and Spiritual Struggles Scale (RSSS), which was created by Exline et al. (2014). Six subscales are evaluated by the 26-item scale: doubt, moral struggles, interpersonal struggles, demon struggles, and divine struggles. Participants rated their experience of each scenario on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 ("not at all") to 5 ("a great deal"). The RSSS demonstrates strong psychometric properties, including excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .91$) and convergent validity, with significant correlations to anger toward God ($r = .49, p < .01$) and religious fear and guilt ($r = .55, p < .01$) as shown in Exline et al. (2014) among a

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sample of U.S. community adults. In this study, the overall Cronbach alpha was .890, with subscale values ranging from .572 to .738. It's worth noting that a Cronbach alpha of 0.5 is considered acceptable for most subscales (Ajah, 2016), further supporting the scale's reliability.

Procedure

The researchers employed a stratified random sampling. Two research assistants, who were thoroughly trained in data collection procedures, were employed to distribute copies of the questionnaire to the selected students. The research assistants were instructed to ensure that every student had a fair chance of being selected, without any preconceived notions or biases. The sampling frame for this study included all students at Nasarawa State University, Keffi, which has around 50 departments across eight faculties. To get a well-rounded sample, the researchers used stratified random sampling. They assigned a number to represent each department, wrote it on individual pieces of paper, and placed each paper into one of eight baskets corresponding to the respective faculties. By randomly drawing two papers from each basket, they ensured that departments were selected without bias. This approach allowed for a fair representation of different departments, capturing a variety of student perspectives. After identifying the selected departments, the researchers applied random sampling to choose individual students from those groups, giving each student an equal shot at being included.

Ethical considerations

A letter of authorization from the psychology department of Nasarawa State University, Keffi, provided institutional approval. The researchers provided participants with a consent form outlining their rights to

voluntary participation and confidentiality, and only individuals who signed the consent form were included. Additionally, respondents were made aware of their freedom to leave the study at any time if they were unhappy with it. Furthermore, no identifying information, like names or contact information, was included in the questionnaire. Participants received guarantees that their answers would be kept private and used only for scholarly research. Throughout the study, these measures guaranteed the privacy and liberty of the participants.

Result

Hypothesis 1: There will be a significant influence of academic entitlement on spiritual struggle,

Table 1: T-test summary table demonstrating the combined prediction of academic entitlement on spiritual struggle

					df	t-test	p	significance
	Academic Entitlement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation				
Spiritual struggle	high	52	2.59	.75	156	3.12	.00	significant
	low	106	2.23	.65				
Divine struggle	high	52	2.14	.83	156	.71	.48	Not-significant
	low	106	2.04	.82				
Demonic struggle	high	52	1.91	.74	156	.63	.52	Not significant
	low	106	1.83	.78				
Interpersonal struggle	high	52	2.79	1.15	156	1.87	.06	Not significant
	low	106	2.45	1.05				
Moral Struggle	high	52	3.22	1.08	156	3.77	.00	significant
	low	106	2.65	.94				
Religious doubt	high	52	3.02	.95	156	4.08	.00	significant
	low	106	2.40	.88				
Ultimate meaning	high	52	2.75	1.08	156	3.83	.00	Significant
	low	106	2.15	.86				

The results presented in Table 1 indicate a significant positive correlation between academic entitlement and spiritual struggle ($t = 3.12, p < 0.05$). Specifically, students who scored higher on academic entitlement ($M = 2.59, SD = 0.75$) reported higher scores on spiritual struggle compared to those with lower scores on academic entitlement ($M = 2.23, SD = 0.65$). In contrast, there was no significant difference between highly entitled students ($M = 2.14, SD = 0.83$) and lowly entitled students ($M = 2.04, SD = 0.82$) on divine struggle ($t = 0.71, p > 0.05$). Similarly, academic entitlement had no significant influence on demonic struggle ($t = 0.63, p > 0.05$).

The findings also showed that while highly entitled students ($M = 2.79, SD = 1.15$) scored slightly higher than lowly entitled persons ($M = 2.45, SD = 1.05$) on interpersonal struggle, the difference was not significant ($t = 1.87, p > 0.06$). Additionally, academic entitlement had a significant positive influence on moral struggle ($t = 3.77, p < 0.05$), with higher scores on academic entitlement ($M = 3.22, SD =$

1.08) corresponding to higher scores on moral struggle compared to lowly entitled students ($M = 2.65, SD = 0.94$).

The results indicate a significant positive correlation between academic entitlement and religious doubt ($t = 4.08, p < 0.05$). Specifically, participants who scored higher on academic entitlement ($M = 3.02, SD = 0.95$) exhibited higher levels of religious doubt compared to those with lower scores on academic entitlement ($M = 2.40, SD = 0.88$). This suggests that individuals who feel more entitled to academic success and achievement are more likely to experience uncertainty and doubt about their religious beliefs. Furthermore, the study found a significant positive influence of academic entitlement on ultimate meaning struggle ($t = 3.83, p < 0.05$). This implies that individuals who score higher on academic entitlement ($M = 2.75, SD = 1.08$) tend to report higher levels of spiritual struggle compared to those with lower scores on academic entitlement ($M = 2.15, SD = 0.86$). This finding suggests that the pursuit of academic success and achievement may be

linked to feelings of spiritual emptiness and disconnection.

Table 2: T-test summary table demonstrating the combined prediction of academic entitlement on envy

Hypothesis 2: There will be a significant influence of academic entitlement on envy.

Group Statistics								
	Academic Entitlement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	S.E	t-test	P	significance
Malign envy	high	52	11.04	4.79	.50			
	low	106	7.98	4.15	.59	4.08	.00	significant
Benign	high	52	18.81	3.62	.67	.		
	low	106	15.03	6.16	.40	4.13	.00	significant

A comparison of the means revealed significant differences in both malign envy ($t = 4.08, p < 0.05$) and benign envy ($t = 4.13, p < 0.05$) scores between highly entitled and lowly entitled students. Notably, highly entitled students exhibited higher levels of malign envy ($M = 11.04, SD = 4.79$) compared to their lowly entitled counterparts ($M = 7.98, SD = 4.16$). Additionally, highly entitled students reported higher levels of benign envy ($M = 18.81, SD = 3.62$) compared to lowly entitled students ($M =$

$15.03, SD = 6.16$). These findings suggest that individuals with higher levels of academic entitlement tend to experience more intense feelings of both positive and negative envy compared to those with lower levels of entitlement.

H3: There will be a significant influence of envy on spiritual struggle

Table 3 is a t-test showing the influence of envy on spiritual struggle.

Malign Envy

Struggle Type	Group	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-test	p-value	Significance
Spiritual Struggle	High	14	3.03	0.55	156	3.92	0.00	Significant
	Low	144	2.29	0.69				
Divine Struggle	High	14	2.49	0.46	156	1.94	0.05	Not Significant
	Low	144	2.04	0.85				
Demonic Struggle	High	14	2.60	0.91	156	3.93	0.02	Significant
	Low	144	1.79	0.72				
Interpersonal Struggle	High	14	3.75	1.12	156	4.48	0.00	Significant
	Low	144	2.46	1.02				
Moral Struggle	High	14	3.18	0.88	156	1.29	0.19	Not Significant
	Low	144	2.80	1.03				
Religious Doubt	High	14	3.18	0.68	156	2.38	0.02	Significant
	Low	144	2.56	0.96				
Ultimate Meaning	High	14	3.25	0.59	156	3.74	0.00	Significant
	Low	144	2.66	0.97				

Benign Envy

Struggle Type	Group	N	Mean	S.D	Df	t-test	p-value	Significance
Spiritual Struggle	High	104	2.48	0.62	156	3.35	0.00	Significant
	Low	54	2.10	0.80				
Divine Struggle	High	104	2.09	0.73	156	0.26	0.79	Not Significant
	Low	54	2.06	1.00				
Demonic Struggle	High	104	2.00	0.70	156	3.04	0.00	Significant
	Low	54	1.60	0.85				
Interpersonal Struggle	High	104	2.70	1.06	156	2.16	0.03	Significant
	Low	54	2.31	1.13				
Moral Struggle	High	104	3.13	0.96	156	5.31	0.00	Significant
	Low	54	2.29	0.90				
Religious Doubt	High	104	2.79	0.82	156	3.42	0.00	Significant
	Low	54	2.26	1.10				
Ultimate Meaning	High	104	2.43	0.97	156	1.37	0.17	Not Significant
	Low	54	2.30	1.00				

Table 3 reveals a significant positive relationship between both malign and benign envy and spiritual struggle. Specifically, individuals who scored higher on malign envy ($t = 3.92, p < 0.05$) and benign envy ($t = 3.35, p < 0.05$) reported higher levels of spiritual struggle compared to those with lower scores on both traits. This pattern was also observed across the three subscales of the spiritual struggle scale. The results indicate that both malign and benign envy have a significant positive influence on demonic struggle, with higher scorers on malign envy ($t = 3.93, p < 0.05$) and benign envy ($t = 3.04, p < 0.05$) reporting higher levels of demonic struggle compared to those with lower scores.

Furthermore, the results show that both malign and benign envy have a significant positive influence on interpersonal struggles ($t = 4.48, p < 0.05$ for malign envy; $t = 2.16, p < 0.05$ for benign envy), indicating that individuals who experience higher levels of both types of envy tend to report higher levels of interpersonal struggle compared to those with lower scores on both traits. Finally, the

findings suggest that both malign and benign envy have a significant positive influence on religious doubt ($t = 2.38, p < 0.05$ for malign envy; $t = 3.42, p < 0.05$ for benign envy), implying that higher scores on both types of envy predict higher levels of religious doubt.

Contrary to expectations, no significant differences were found between highly malign envious students ($M = 3.03, SD = 0.55$) and lowly malign envious students ($M = 2.29, SD = 0.69$) in terms of their scores on divine struggle ($t(1,94) = 1.94, p > 0.05$). Similarly, no significant difference was observed between highly benign envious students ($M = 3.18, SD = 0.88$) and lowly benign envious students ($M = 2.80, SD = 1.03$) on their scores on divine struggle ($t(1,26) = 0.26, p > 0.05$).

Analysis revealed conflicting results between two of the spiritual struggle subscales. On the moral struggle subscale, there was no significant difference found between highly malign envious students ($M = 2.14, SD = 0.83$) and lowly malign envious students ($M =$

2.04, SD = 0.82) ($t(1,29) = 1.29, p > 0.05$). In contrast, a significant difference was observed between highly benign envious students ($M = 3.13, SD = 0.96$) and lowly benign envious students ($M = 2.29, SD = 0.90$) on their scores on moral struggle ($t(1,26) = 5.31, p < 0.05$).

A similar pattern emerged on the ultimate meaning struggle subscale. The results showed a significant influence of malign envy on ultimate meaning struggle ($t(1,29) = 3.74, p < 0.05$). Specifically, those with high malign envy ($M = 3.25, SD = 0.59$) differed significantly from those with low malign envy ($M = 2.66, SD = 0.97$) in their scores on ultimate meaning struggle.

In contrast, no significant difference was found between highly benign envious students ($M = 2.43, SD = 0.97$) and lowly benign envious students ($M = 2.30, SD = 1.00$) on their scores on divine struggle ($t(1,26) = 1.37, p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that the relationship between envy and spiritual struggle may vary depending on the specific type of envy and the aspect of spiritual struggle being measured.

H4: There will be a mediating effect of benign envy on the relationship between academic entitlement and spiritual struggle.

Table 4: Mediating role of benign envy in the influence of academic entitlement on spiritual struggle

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		Z	p
			Lower	Upper		
Indirect	0.183	0.0768	0.0328	0.334	2.39	0.017
Direct	0.310	0.1348	0.0458	0.574	2.30	0.021
Total	0.493	0.1152	0.2675	0.719	4.28	< .001

The results in Table 4 show that academic entitlement affects spiritual struggle in two ways—directly and indirectly through benign envy. The indirect effect (0.183, $p = 0.017$) suggests that benign envy helps explain how academic entitlement leads to spiritual struggle. However, the direct effect (0.310, $p = 0.021$) is also significant, meaning academic entitlement influences spiritual struggle on its own, not just through benign envy. Since both direct and indirect effects matter, this means that benign envy only partly explains the connection. The total effect (0.493, $p < .001$) confirms that academic entitlement strongly predicts spiritual struggle. So, while benign

envy does play a role as a mediator, it doesn't fully account for the link.

Discussion

The purpose of the study is to investigate the mediating role of envy in the influence of academic entitlement on spiritual struggle. Understanding these differences can provide deeper insight into how entitlement shapes spiritual experiences. The findings of this study align with past research indicating that academic entitlement can lead to negative emotional outcomes, including spiritual struggles. Prior studies suggest that students with high levels of entitlement often experience frustration and disappointment

when faced with academic setbacks (Tobechi & Elvis, 2023; Grubbs et al., 2013), which can manifest as a crisis of faith and disconnection from spiritual beliefs (Zitek & Jordan, 2019). This correlation aligns with the notion that a sense of entitlement can shift focus away from personal accountability and growth, thereby intensifying feelings of disconnection from a higher power (Muhamad et al., 2022).

The second hypothesis, which states that academic entitlement will predict envy, was confirmed. This result is consistent with that of Irshad et al. (2024), who found a strong link between entitlement and envy. The research findings support the idea that academic entitlement is a catalyst for both benign and malign envy, consistent with previous literature that identifies entitlement as fostering feelings of inferiority when comparing oneself to others (Grubbs et al., 2014; Rahaei & Salehzadeh, 2020). Entitled students may feel malicious envy when they perceive others as achieving what they believe is rightfully theirs, leading to resentment (Smith & Kim, 2007). Conversely, benign envy may emerge as a motivation for self-improvement (Lange & Crusius, 2015).

The third hypothesis, which states that there will be a significant influence of benign and malign envy on spiritual struggles, was also partially confirmed, as the study produced mixed findings. Findings from this study showed that both benign and malicious envy contribute to spiritual struggles, but in different ways. Malicious envy strongly influences struggles related to spirituality, interpersonal relationships, religious doubt, and a sense of purpose. This aligns with past studies that link envy to frustration, resentment, and feelings of being lost or disconnected (Kaminger et al., 2023; Grubbs et al., 2013). Benign envy, while often seen as motivating, also plays a role in spiritual and moral struggles, as well as religious doubt. This supports earlier research suggesting that

constantly comparing oneself to others can lead to self-doubt and dissatisfaction (Lange & Crusius, 2015; Rahaei & Salehzadeh, 2020). However, unlike previous studies, this research found that benign envy does not significantly affect one's sense of ultimate meaning, which challenges the idea that envy always weakens personal purpose (Muhamad et al., 2022).

The results showed that while benign envy was linked to moral struggle, malignant envy was not. Malignant envy, driven by resentment and hostility, often leads to self-serving behaviour that disregards moral values (Smith & Kim, 2017). In contrast, benign envy fosters moral struggle by encouraging ethical reflection and a desire to succeed through fair means. Because malignant envy lacks empathy, it becomes difficult to consider the feelings of the envied person, leading to moral dilemmas. Meanwhile, benign envy promotes empathy, helping individuals recognize the impact of their actions on others and guiding moral decision-making. This aligns with Lange et al. (2018), who found that malignant envy was associated with psychopathic traits, whereas benign envy was linked to lower emotional detachment, impulsivity, and psychopathy.

The fourth hypothesis was confirmed as benign envy was found to mediate the relationship between academic entitlement and spiritual struggle. The findings align with past research demonstrating envy's mediating role in the influence of entitlement on various outcomes. For instance, Van Dijk et al. (2019) showed that envy mediated the impact of entitlement on individuals' perception of a destination, while Farid et al. (2025) found that envy mediated the relationship between psychological entitlement and both engagement in learning and psychological anxiety. Similarly, the current study confirms that benign envy mediates the influence of

academic entitlement on spiritual struggle. However, unlike Farid et al. (2025), where entitlement had no direct effect, the present findings indicate that academic entitlement directly influences spiritual struggle in addition to the indirect effect through envy.

Conclusion

This study looked into how feelings of academic entitlement and envy might affect the spiritual struggles university students face, and what that could mean for managing their well-being. The results showed that students with a strong sense of academic entitlement tended to experience more spiritual challenges, such as struggles with their faith, morality, sense of purpose, and relationships with others. Interestingly, those with higher academic entitlement also reported experiencing more envy—both the kind that can be harmful (malign envy) and the kind that's less destructive (benign envy). The study found that harmful envy was linked to more spiritual struggles, while less harmful envy seemed to have the opposite effect, reducing these struggles.

This study offers important insights into how psychological entitlement, envy, and spiritual struggles are connected among students. However, there are a few limitations to consider. Since the study only looked at correlations, we can't say for sure that one causes the other. Also, because the data relies on self-reports, there's a chance that social pressures could influence how students answered. To improve on this, future research could use experimental methods and objective measures to get more reliable results. It would also help to include a wider range of students from different educational and cultural backgrounds to make the findings more applicable to everyone. Long-term studies could track changes over time, which would be helpful for providing early support. Lastly, interventions focused on changing entitlement

attitudes and helping students manage envy could go a long way in improving both their well-being and academic success.

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